

Resilience, Growth, and the Future of the UJOC

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Welcome to Volume 4, Issue 1 of the *Utah Journal of Communication*.

The publication of each issue provides an opportunity to reflect not only on the scholarship contained within its pages, but also on the continued growth and evolution of the journal itself. As we begin our fourth volume, I find myself particularly grateful for the community of scholars, educators, reviewers, and readers who have contributed to the success of this publication. What began as an effort to create an accessible, peer-reviewed outlet for communication scholarship has steadily matured into a journal that attracts diverse voices, meaningful research, and innovative pedagogical contributions from across the discipline.

With the publication of the eight articles featured in this issue, the UJOC has now published 66 articles since its founding while maintaining a 46.2% acceptance rate. These milestones represent more than simple statistics. They reflect hundreds of hours of work by authors developing manuscripts, reviewers providing constructive feedback, editors guiding submissions through the publication process, and readers engaging with the scholarship we publish. Most importantly, they represent a growing community of communication scholars committed to advancing knowledge and improving communication education.

Like any academic endeavor, growth is rarely linear. Over the past year, the journal has experienced a number of transitions that tested our adaptability while simultaneously demonstrating the resilience of our editorial team. Members of the editorial board completed their service and moved on to new opportunities, while one member of our managing board accepted a faculty position at another university. We also navigated unexpected WordPress and website challenges that occasionally complicated the publication process. While these obstacles often occurred behind the scenes, they served as important reminders that successful journals are sustained through collaboration, patience, and a shared commitment to scholarly excellence.

This issue also marks a transition within our editorial team. We extend our sincere gratitude to Dr. L. Paul Husselbee, who recently retired from his role as Book Review Editor. Dr. Husselbee's service, expertise, and dedication have contributed greatly to the development of the UJOC, and we are grateful for the time and energy he invested in helping the journal grow during its formative years. We wish him nothing but success and fulfillment in his future endeavors.

At the same time, we are pleased to welcome Dr. Giuliano McDonald to our editorial board. Dr. McDonald recently completed his Ph.D. at the University of Miami and successfully defended his dissertation before accepting a tenure-track position in sport communication at Southern Utah University. His expertise, enthusiasm, and fresh perspective will undoubtedly strengthen the journal as we continue to expand our reach and impact. We are excited to have him join our team and look forward to his contributions in the years ahead.

The articles featured in this issue collectively demonstrate the breadth of contemporary communication scholarship while highlighting the increasingly complex relationship between communication, technology, institutions, and human experience.

The first research article, a brief report authored by Lindsay Fullerton (2026), examines whether college students' stated motivations for social media use align with the content they actually encounter on their social media feeds. Using Uses and Gratifications Theory as a framework, the study identifies themes such as advertisement overload, surveillance-based personalization, escapism, and goal misalignment.

Sakilé K. Camara (2026) explores student perceptions of artificial intelligence-generated interview evaluations. As AI becomes increasingly integrated into hiring processes, the study raises important questions regarding transparency, trust, and the limitations of algorithmic communication assessment.

The international scope of the issue is expanded through Qin Zhang's (2026) examination of media use in interpersonal conflict among college students in mainland China. The findings highlight the growing role of WeChat and other digital platforms in conflict management while demonstrating that communication satisfaction remains similar across mediated and face-to-face interactions.

The issue's final peer-reviewed research article is adapted from a master's thesis by Maddi Gerhardt (2026). Guided by the Theory of Institutional Athletic Privilege, the study examines how branding, reputation, and lived experience shape student-athletes' perceptions of athletic facilities and organizational resources.

In addition to these original research contributions, this issue features three GIFT (Great Ideas for Teaching) articles designed to support communication educators through practical, classroom-tested activities.

Heather Smith (2026) presents an instructional activity focused on grief and supportive communication. The activity provides students with opportunities to discuss grief, supportive listening, and effective communication during times of loss.

Jacquelyn K. Seymour and Katherine P. Johnson (2026) explore the use of custom, closed-loop AI chatbots to enhance student engagement with course syllabi and exam preparation. Their contribution offers a practical model for incorporating artificial intelligence into communication education while maintaining privacy and instructional control.

Finally, Sophia Koleno and Bilal Al-Zubaidi (2026) introduce an activity focused on ethical AI-assisted brainstorming and reflective topic development. Their work encourages students to engage critically with generative AI while maintaining ownership of the creative and decision-making processes involved in learning.

Taken together, the articles in this issue illustrate the remarkable breadth of the communication discipline. They examine social media, artificial intelligence, interpersonal conflict, collegiate athletics, grief communication, and innovative pedagogical practices. While these topics may appear distinct, they are united by a common focus on understanding how communication shapes human behavior, relationships, institutions, and society. They also demonstrate the ways communication scholarship continues to evolve alongside technological innovation and changing social realities.

Another aspect of this issue worth celebrating is the diversity of voices represented among our contributors. The authors featured in this volume include established scholars, assistant professors, doctoral candidates, lecturers, recent graduates, and emerging researchers. Their collective contributions reinforce an important belief held by the Utah Journal of Communication

since its founding: meaningful scholarship can emerge from every stage of an academic career. By creating opportunities for both established and emerging scholars, we strengthen not only the journal but also the discipline as a whole.

As the UJOC enters its fourth volume, we remain committed to fostering scholarly dialogue, supporting innovative teaching practices, and providing an accessible venue for communication research. The continued success of this journal is a testament to the many individuals who contribute their expertise and energy to the publication process. To our authors, reviewers, editorial board members, and readers, thank you for your continued support and belief in the mission of this journal.

We hope the scholarship featured in this issue informs your research, enriches your teaching, and inspires future inquiry. We look forward to continuing this journey together as the Utah Journal of Communication grows and evolves in the years ahead.

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